

The Effect of Motivation on Employee Performance through Organizational Culture

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to determine the effect of motivation on employee performance through organizational culture variables at the Pasuruan City Civil Service Police Unit. This research is an explanatory research (explanatory research) which aims to test the proposed hypothesis about the effect of motivation on employee performance and organizational culture. This study uses quantitative data analysis with path analysis and classical assumption test using non-probability sampling technique, namely saturated sampling (census). The population and sample in this study were all employees at the Pasuruan City Civil Service Police Unit with a total of 104 employees. From the results of this study indicate that (1) motivation has a direct and significant effect on employee performance, (2) motivation has a direct and significant effect on organizational culture, (3) organizational culture has a direct effect on employee performance, and (4) organizational culture can mediate indirectly between motivation and employee performance.

KEYWORDS: Motivation, Employee Performance, Organizational Culture

INTRODUCTION

The success of an organization is influenced by the individual performance of its employees, an organization will seek to improve the performance of its employees in the hope that the company's goals can be achieved. Performance is basically what employees do or don't do. Employee performance is what influences how much they contribute to the organization including output quantity, output quality, output period, workplace attendance and cooperative attitude, Mathis and Jackson, (2002).

Azar and Shafighi, (2013:2) states that one reason for the success of employees and organizations is because of the high motivation factor and the concept of motivation used to explain abilities and work opportunities. Motivation is a factor that leads to behavior in organizations. Inside a person will always have a motivation that is used to move his behavior in meeting certain goals. Employee motivation can be influenced by factors of interest, salary received, need for security, interpersonal relationships and opportunities to work. With motivation, it can stimulate employees to move more energy and thoughts in realizing company goals. If the need for this is met, there will be satisfaction and smoothness for improving employee performance.

The Pasuruan City Civil Service Police Unit Office is an instrument of the Regional Government in maintaining peace and public order and enforcing Regional Regulations. Satpol PP has the task and responsibility of assisting the Regional Head to create a peaceful, orderly and orderly regional condition so that the administration of the wheels of government can run smoothly and the community can carry out their activities safely. Employees of the Civil Service Police Unit (Satpol PP) as one of the main elements of the Regional apparatus' human resources have an important role in enforcing Regional Regulations and/or Mayor Regulations, maintaining public order and public peace and protecting the community.

To optimize the performance of Satpol PP, it is necessary to build institutions that are able to support the realization of a peaceful, orderly and orderly regional condition. The Satpol PP institutional arrangement does not only consider the criteria for the population density of an area, but also the burden of duties and responsibilities carried out, such as culture, sociology, and the safety risks of Satpol PP. For this reason, it is necessary to increase human resources for Satpol PP employees.

There are facts on the ground that the performance conditions in the Pamong Praja Police Unit of the Pasuruan City Government are currently not good, this can be seen from the first indicators, employees often use time for other purposes other than working hours, both employees are often absent at work and are also disciplined at work. diligently is still considered lacking, the three employees' abilities in serving the community are still considered less in accordance with the targets of the

The Effect of Motivation on Employee Performance through Organizational Culture

programs being run, considering the demands for government officials to improve employee performance, it must also be balanced with efforts to improve the quality of government officials physically and non-physical. With the encouragement of motivation from organizational leaders to their subordinates and discipline in working and obeying existing regulations in the organization, there will be a change in attitude and work spirit to improve the performance of all apparatus/employees.

The theory and empirical facts that have been described above, in this study will be developed a form of research aimed at analyzing "The Influence of Motivation on Employee Performance Through Organizational Culture Variables at the Pasuruan City Civil Service Police Unit."

LITERATURE REVIEW

Motivation

Yusuf, (2015:263), the motivation comes from the word "Movere" which means "Impulse or driving force". Motivation is the driving force in a person in working to fulfill the goals to be achieved,

According to Sutrisno (2009:116) there are factors that influence motivation, namely internal and external factors. Internal factors that can affect the motivation of a person include: the desire to live, the desire to have, the desire to gain appreciation, the desire to gain recognition, the desire to power. External factors are also no less important in weakening work motivation. External factors are: working environment conditions, adequate compensation, good supervision, job security, status and responsibilities, flexible regulations.

Several researchers like Dharma, (2017) and Annisa and Supriyanto, (2021), have tested the effect of motivation on employee performance, among others showing that motivation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. Sembiring Hendri, (2020) shows that motivation and work environment have a positive and significant effect on employee performance at Bank Sinarmas Medan. Meanwhile, with the same theme, research has also been carried out by (Susanty and Baskoro, 2012) showing that motivation has no significant effect on employee performance. Different results are also shown by research conducted (Murti & Srimulyani, 2013) showing that motivation does not directly affect employee performance.

Employee Performance

Performance comes from the word Job Performance or Actual Performance (job performance achieved by an employee). Performance is the result of work achieved by an employee in accordance with his responsibilities both in quantity and quality (Mangkunegara, 2015: 67). Employee performance can be evaluated objectively and accurately through performance level benchmarks. This measurement means providing an opportunity for employees to know their level of performance.

Organizational culture

In managing the company, managers are familiar with and apply modern management principles, such as the use of structures, systems, strategies and so on, although there are some companies that still use traditional organizational culture.

According to Sutrisno (2010: 2), organizational culture is an invisible social force that can move people in an organization to carry out work activities. However, Tobari (2014: 54) argues that organizational culture is between chaos and calm, or continuity and change. Organizational culture is also a form as an assumption that is owned, accepted implicitly by the group and determines how the group feels, thinks, and reacts to its diverse environment (Moeheriono, 2012:335). According to Bismala et al (2015:164) culture in organizations plays at least three important roles, namely providing identity for its members, increasing commitment to the organization's vision and mission and strengthening behavioral standards.

Diana, et al, 2021, show that Organizational culture has a significant effect is able to improve employee performance. Research on organizational culture on employee performance has been conducted by (Astutik, 2016) found that work discipline (X1) and organizational culture (X2) have a positive and significant effect on employee performance (Y), both partially and simultaneously. (Hidayah & Nazaruddin, 2017) shows that leadership style, organizational culture, work motivation, and work discipline have a significant effect on employee performance.

(Aditya & Nugraheni, 2014) shows that there is a positive and significant influence between motivation on employee performance and organizational culture as a moderating variable. Nadhiroh, (2019) explains that simultaneously or simultaneously, the independent variables of motivation, job satisfaction and the dependent variable of employee performance and organizational culture as moderating variables affect the dependent variable, namely employee performance.

RESEARCH METHODS

This study uses a quantitative research approach with a research measuring instrument in the form of a questionnaire which is directly given to the respondents. The data obtained in the form of answers from employees to the questions asked. Based on

The Effect of Motivation on Employee Performance through Organizational Culture

the research objectives that have been determined, this type of research is explanatory research, which is to test the hypothesized variables. This research has a hypothesis that will be tested for truth. This hypothesis describes the relationship between two variables, to find out whether the variable is associated or not with other variables, or whether the variable is caused or influenced or not by other variables (Supriyanto and Mashuri, 2013: 180).

This research was conducted at the Pasuruan City Civil Service Police Unit. The population used in this study were all employees of the Pasuruan City Civil Service Police Unit, totaling 104 people.

This study uses the Non Probability Sampling technique, which according to Sugiyono (2001) means a technique that does not provide equal opportunities/opportunities for each element or member of the population to be selected as samples. The selected non-probability sampling technique is saturated sampling (census), which is a sampling method when all members of the population are used as samples. In this study, samples taken were all employees of the Pasuruan City Civil Service Police Unit, namely 104 people consisting of several employees who had different positions. The sampling technique used was the saturated sample method. The saturated sample method is a sampling technique when all members of the population are used as samples. The data analysis tool used in this research is Path Analysis and uses SPSS 16 software.

RESEARCH METHODS AND MATERIAL

Quantitative Data Analysis

Based on data obtained from the Pasuruan City Civil Service Police Unit, the number of questionnaires distributed to the respondents was 104 questionnaires. To determine the sample in this study, the saturated sampling method (census) is used, namely the sampling method when all members of the population are used as samples. The results of the sample size and description of respondents are as follows:

Table 1. Description of Respondents

No	Respondent Description	amount	Percentage
1.	Gender:		
	Man	72	69.2%
	girl	32	30.8%
Total		104	100%
2.	Respondent Age:		
	35-41 Year	49	47.1%
	42-49 Year	33	31.7%
	50-56 Year	22	21.1%
Total		104	100%
3.	Last education:		
	SMA/SMK	81	77.9%
	S1	14	13.5%
	S2	9	8.7%
Total		104	100%
4.	Length of work:		
	6-10 Year	40	38.5%
	11-15 Year	43	41.3%
	16-20 Year	21	20.2%
Total		104	100%

The structural model of this research can be seen in the following figure:

Figure 1. Structural Model of Research on the Effect of Motivation on Employee Performance Through Organizational Culture Variables

The Effect of Motivation on Employee Performance through Organizational Culture

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The decision making for hypothesis testing uses the t-statistical value, where the t-statistic value is greater than the t-table value (1.659) indicating a significant influence. The following table shows the results of hypothesis testing.

Table 3. Direct and Indirect Test Results

Hypothesis	Influence	Coefficient	t-statistics	Significant	Information
1	X ke Y	0.467	4.382	0.000	Significant
2	X ke Z	0.699	9.875	0.000	Significant
3	Z ke Y	0.218	2.032	0.045	Significant
4	X ke Z ke Y	0.152	9.875	0.000	Significant

The Direct Effect of Motivation on Employee Performance

Based on the results of the path analysis test, it shows that the motivation variable has a significant effect on employee performance $0.000 < 0.05$. with a standardized beta value of 0.467. So it can be concluded that motivation directly has a significant effect on employee performance.

This is in line with research by (Dharma, 2017) showing that motivation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. Work motivation is something that gives rise to encouragement or enthusiasm for work or in other words it encourages work spirit (Martoyo, 1996:154). Without motivation, an employee cannot fulfill his work according to standards or exceed standards because what motivates him to work is not fulfilled. Even if an employee who has the ability to work high but does not have the motivation to complete his task, the final result in his work will not be satisfactory. This proves that motivation has an influence on employee performance.

Work motivation in the view of Islam also means that doing something must be enthusiastic, optimistic, and full of joy. This is because the grace of Allah SWT is always there at all times and everywhere. As explained in the word of Allah SWT in the Qur'an Surah Yusuf, verse 87 it is explained that: Meaning: "O my children, go you, then seek news about Joseph and his brother and do not despair of the mercy of Allah. Verily, no one despairs of the mercy of Allah, except a people who disbelieve."

From the verse it is very clear that despair is only for those who disbelieve. Out of desperation can lead to other things that can violate religious rules and even state law, such as suicide, robbing and others. For that, don't give up whatever we experience. Indeed, sustenance and grace come from Allah SWT, not from humans or other creatures.

According to Hidayatullah (2012: 30) do not give up hope because Allah will not change a person's fate, if that person does not intend to change his fate. Likewise, when we are in an organizational environment or in our work environment, we need motivation to continue to spur our enthusiasm so that the spirit does not decrease. A good company or organization is an organization that can motivate its employees to get the desired production.

The Direct Effect of Motivation on Organizational Culture

Based on the results of the path analysis test, it shows that the motivation variable has a significant influence on organizational culture $0.000 < 0.05$. with a standardized beta value of 0.699. So it can be concluded that motivation directly has a significant effect on organizational culture.

This is in line with research according to (Djafri Novianty, 2015) which shows that there is a direct positive influence on leadership style, principal's empathy, motivation on school organizational culture. There is a direct positive influence of leadership style on empathy and motivation of principals. (Efendy, Herlambang, & Rozaid, 2018) shows that motivation and commitment have a significant effect on organizational culture and employee performance.

Direct Influence of Organizational Culture on Employee Performance

Based on the results of the path analysis test, it shows that the organizational culture variable has a significant influence on employee performance $0.045 < 0.05$. with a standardized beta value of 0.218. So it can be concluded that organizational culture directly has a significant effect on employee performance.

The results of this study are in line with research according to Gibson (1997) The company will not be separated from the role and contribution of every employee in the organization, if employees in the company do not obey the organizational culture or are not familiar with the existing culture, the employee's performance has not been maximized in the organization. , and this can affect employee performance. Organizational culture is a shared belief value that underlies corporate identity. The virtue of organizational culture is the control and direction in shaping human attitudes and behaviors that involve themselves in

The Effect of Motivation on Employee Performance through Organizational Culture

an organizational activity. Organizational culture as a system that penetrates the values, beliefs, and norms that exist in every organization.

The Effect of Motivation on Employee Performance through Organizational Culture Variables

Based on the results of the study, it shows that the influence of the motivational variable on employee performance through organizational culture is proven in the path effect test of 0.152 and the comparison of t count with t table $9,875 > 1,659$ it can be concluded that organizational culture can mediate the direct influence between motivational variables on employee performance. This means that organizational culture can affect motivation in improving employee performance in the agency.

The results of this study are in line with research according to Aditya (2014) which shows that there is an influence between motivation on employee performance with organizational culture as a moderating variable. Nadhiroh, (2019), shows that motivation and job satisfaction have an effect on employee performance, while organizational culture has no effect on employee performance. Simultaneously, the independent variables motivation, job satisfaction and the dependent variable employee performance and organizational culture as moderating variables affect the dependent variable, namely Employee Performance.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Based on the research that has been done, it can be concluded that 1) Motivation has an effect on employee performance; 2) Motivation has a direct and significant effect on organizational culture; 3) Organizational culture has a direct effect on employee performance; 4) Organizational culture can indirectly mediate between motivation and employee performance.

Suggestion

Based on the results of the analysis and the limitations in this study, it is hoped that in future research to use different or varied mediating variables to examine the relationship between motivation and employee performance with different research results that will complement each other.

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The Effect of Motivation on Employee Performance through Organizational Culture

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